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CLASSIFICATION OF VEHICLES BASED ON AUDIO SIGNALS USING QUADRATIC DISCRIMINANT ANALYSIS AND HIGH ENERGY FEATURE VECTORS

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ABSTRACT

The focus of this paper is on classification of different vehicles using sound emanated from the vehicles. In this paper, quadratic discriminant analysis classifies audio signals of passing vehicles to bus, car, motor, and truck categories based on features such as short time energy, average zero cross rate, and pitch frequency of periodic segments of signals. Simulation results show that just by considering high energy feature vectors, better classification accuracy can be achieved due to the correspondence of low energy regions with noises of the background. To separate these elements, short time energy and average zero cross rate are used simultaneously. In our method, we have used a few features which are easy to be calculated in time domain and enable practical implementation of efficient classifier. Although, the computation complexity is low, the classification accuracy is comparable with other classification methods based on long feature vectors reported in literature for this problem.

KEYWORD

Classification accuracy; Periodic segments; Quadratic Discriminant Analysis; Separation criterion; Short time analysis.

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DETERMINATION OF OVER-LEARNING AND OVER-FITTING PROBLEM IN BACK PROPAGATION NEURAL NETWORK

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ABSTRACT

A drawback of the error-back propagation algorithm for a multilayer feed forward neural network is over learning or over fitting. We have discussed this problem, and obtained necessary and sufficient Experiment and conditions for over-learning problem to arise. Using those conditions and the concept of a reproducing, this paper proposes methods for choosing training set which is used to prevent over-learning. For a classifier, besides classification capability, its size is another fundamental aspect. In pursuit of high performance, many classifiers do not take into consideration their sizes and contain numerous both essential and insignificant rules. This, however, may bring adverse situation to classifier, for its efficiency will be put down greatly by redundant rules. Hence, it is necessary to eliminate those unwanted rules. We have discussed various experiments with and without over learning or over fitting problem.

KEYWORDS

Neural Network, learning, Hidden Neurons, Hidden Layers

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APPLICATION OF GENETIC ALGORITHM OPTIMIZED NEURAL NETWORK CONNECTION WEIGHTS FOR MEDICAL DIAGNOSIS OF PIMA INDIANS DIABETES

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ABSTRACT

Neural Networks are one of many data mining analytical tools that can be utilized to make predictions for medical data. Model selection for a neural network entails various factors such as selection of the optimal number of hidden nodes, selection of the relevant input variables and selection of optimal connection weights. This paper presents the application of hybrid model that integrates Genetic Algorithm and Back Propagation network(BPN) where GA is used to initialize and optimize the connection weights of BPN. Significant features identified by using two methods :Decision tree and GA-CFS method are used as input to the hybrid model to diagnose diabetes mellitus. The results prove that, GA-optimized BPN approach has outperformed the BPN approach without GA optimization. In addition the hybrid GA-BPN with relevant inputs lead to further improvised categorization accuracy compared to results produced by GA-BPN alone with some redundant inputs.

KEYWORDS

Back Propagation Network, Genetic algorithm, connection weight optimisation.

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APPLICATION OF FUZZY LOGIC IN TRANSPORT PLANNING

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ABSTRACT

Fuzzy logic is shown to be a very promising mathematical approach for modelling traffic and transportation processes characterized by subjectivity, ambiguity, uncertainty and imprecision. The basic premises of fuzzy logic systems are presented as well as a detailed analysis of fuzzy logic systems developed to solve various traffic and transportation planning problems. Emphasis is put on the importance of fuzzy logic systems as universal approximators in solving traffic and transportation problems. This paper presents an analysis of the results achieved using fuzzy logic to model complex traffic and transportation processes.

KEYWORDS

Fuzzy Logic, Transportation Planning, Mathematical modeling

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MULTISPECTRAL IMAGE ANALYSIS USING RANDOM FOREST

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ABSTRACT

Classical methods for classification of pixels in multispectral images include supervised classifiers such as the maximum-likelihood classifier, neural network classifiers, fuzzy neural networks, support vector machines, and decision trees. Recently, there has been an increase of interest in ensemble learning – a method that generates many classifiers and aggregates their results. Breiman proposed Random Forest in 2001 for classification and clustering. Random Forest grows many decision trees for classification. To classify a new object, the input vector is run through each decision tree in the forest. Each tree gives a classification. The forest chooses the classification having the most votes. Random Forest provides a robust algorithm for classifying large datasets. The potential of Random Forest is not been explored in analyzing multispectral satellite images. To evaluate the performance of Random Forest, we classified multispectral images using various classifiers such as the maximum likelihood classifier, neural network, support vector machine (SVM), and Random Forest and compare their results.

KEYWORDS

Classification, Decision Trees, Random Forest, Multispectral Images

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HASH FUNCTION IMPLEMENTATION USING ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORK

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ABSTRACT

In this paper an algorithm for one-way hash function construction based on a two layer feed forward neural network along with the piece-wise linear (pwl) chaotic map is proposed. Based on chaotic neural networks, a Hash function is constructed, which makes use of neural networks' diffusion property and chaos' confusion property. This function encodes the plaintext of arbitrary length into the hash value of fixed length (typically, 128-bit, 256-bit or 512-bit). Theoretical analysis and experimental results show that this hash function is one-way, with high key sensitivity and plaintext sensitivity, and secure against birthday attacks or meet-in-the-middle attacks. These properties make it a suitable choice for data signature or authentication.

KEYWORDS

One-way Hash function, Neural network, Chaotic map, Plaintext Sensitivity

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METHODOLOGICAL STUDY OF OPINION MINING AND SENTIMENT ANALYSIS TECHNIQUES

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ABSTRACT

Decision making both on individual and organizational level is always accompanied by the search of other's opinion on the same. With tremendous establishment of opinion rich resources like, reviews, forum discussions, blogs, micro-blogs, Twitter etc provide a rich anthology of sentiments. This user generated content can serve as a benefaction to market if the semantic orientations are deliberated. Opinion mining and sentiment analysis are the formalization for studying and construing opinions and sentiments. The digital ecosystem has itself paved way for use of huge volume of opinionated data recorded. This paper is an attempt to review and evaluate the various techniques used for opinion and sentiment analysis.

KEYWORDS

Opinion Mining, Sentiment Analysis, Feature Extraction Techniques, Naïve Bayes Classifiers, Clustering, Support Vector Machines

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MULTI OBJECTIVE FLEXIBLE JOB SHOP SCHEDULING USING A MODIFIED INVASIVE WEED OPTIMIZATION

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ABSTRACT

Recently, many studies are carried out with inspirations from ecological phenomena for developing optimization techniques. The new algorithm that is motivated by a common phenomenon in agriculture is colonization of invasive weeds. In this paper, a modified invasive weed optimization (IWO) algorithm is presented for optimization of multiobjective flexible job shop scheduling problems (FJSSPs) with the criteria to minimize the maximum completion time (makespan), the total workload of machines and the workload of the critical machine. IWO is a bio-inspired metaheuristic that mimics the ecological behaviour of weeds in colonizing and finding suitable place for growth and reproduction. IWO is developed to solve continuous optimization problems that's why the heuristic rule the Smallest Position Value (SPV) is used to convert the continuous position values to the discrete job sequences. The computational experiments show that the proposed algorithm is highly competitive to the state-of-the-art methods in the literature since it is able to find the optimal and best-known solutions on the instances studied.

KEYWORDS

Invasive Weed Optimization, Metaheuristics, Multiobjective optimization, Flexible job shop scheduling problem, Smallest Position Value.

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A HYBRID MODEL FOR BANKRUPTCY PREDICTION USING GENETIC ALGORITHM, FUZZY C-MEANS AND MARS

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ABSTRACT

Bankruptcy prediction is very important for all the organization since it affects the economy and rise many social problems with high costs. There are large number of techniques have been developed to predict the bankruptcy, which helps the decision makers such as investors and financial analysts. One of the bankruptcy prediction models is the hybrid model using Fuzzy C-means clustering and MARS, which uses static ratios taken from the bank financial statements for prediction, which has its own theoretical advantages. The performance of existing bankruptcy model can be improved by selecting the best features dynamically depend on the nature of the firm. This dynamic selection can be accomplished by Genetic Algorithm and it improves the performance of prediction model. .

KEYWORDS

Bankruptcy prediction, financial ratio models, Genetic Algorithm, Fuzzy c-means Clustering, MARS.

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A DECISION SUPPORT SYSTEM FOR TUBERCULOSIS DIAGNOSABILITY

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ABSTRACT

In order to cope with real-world problems more effectively, we tend to design a decision support system for tuberculosis bacterium class identification. In this paper, we are concerned to propose a fuzzy diagnosability approach, which takes value between {0, 1} and based on observability of events, we formalized the construction of diagnoses that are used to perform diagnosis. In particular, we present a framework of the fuzzy expert system; discuss the suitability of artificial intelligence as a novel soft paradigm and reviews work from the literature for the development of a medical diagnostic system. The newly proposed approach allows us to deal with problems of diagnosability for both crisp and fuzzy value of input data. Accuracy analysis of designed decision support system based on demographic data was done by comparing expert knowledge and system generated response. This basic emblematic approach using fuzzy inference system is presented that describes a technique to forecast the existence of bacterium and provides support platform to pulmonary researchers in identifying the ailment effectively.

KEYWORDS

Expert system, fuzzy diagnosability, rulebased method, MATLAB, Tuberculosis (TB).

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